

GERMANY'S MANUFACTURING FUTURE

For Germany, it's the end of the year, and as Europe's biggest economy there are some vast challenges ahead derive from its increasingly complex relationship with China to climate change. All eyes will be on how German leaders grapple with these issues for there is one German industry that reveals more about the country's prospect, it is cars. Traditionally, the car industry is very powerful there have been open doors to German ministries. The German car industry is a vital part of the economy with links to governments that go back decades. To see Germany's future look at its 2021 cars, the curves, the precision, its cutting-edge engineering like that has helped place carmakers at the heart of the German economy, and the industry has proved a bellwether for the country's readiness too. Since the '70s, car exports have risen with Germany's wealth and influence. Manufacturing is incredibly important in Germany because it represents around 18% of GDP and of course, the car sector represents a very large part of that. It's not quite, the biggest drive in Germany's economy is influenced by the car industry, but the sector is crucial to the future of Germany and the future of its industrial model but that industrial model could be under threat.

After over a century of global dominance, German carmakers are now playing catch-up, and it's not just the car industry that is losing ground. In 2000, seven of the world's most valuable companies were German but in the past two decades, that number has fallen to just three. How have Germany's carmakers attempt to attract back the global market share could be telling for the economy as a whole. Take international relations, almost half of Germany's GDP comes from exports, cars make up the biggest proportion of the GDP. Whom Germany sells cars to matters, it can point to alliances or trouble brewing leading to massive destruction of the economy or thrive. Since 2016, China has been Germany's biggest trading partner. In 1998, German trade with China was worth 16bn Dollars, now it's worth over 180bn Dollars. Likely, fear is there for Germany has become too reliant on the Chinese market. For the past 16 years, Angela Merkel has courted China in the name of the trade, it's an approach that has its risk. Particularly now, we're in the context of this unfolding systemic competition that is between America and China. At least for some people, there is a worry that putting the German economy at stake with the Chinese might leave you exposed to some of the ill winds of geopolitics and geoeconomics that might be heading Germany and Europe's way

in the coming years. There is a strong sense that, Germany's China policy is going to have to be reset and rescanned. Germany's new leader will face the same challenge as its car industry.

How to keep their biggest trading partner onside without ending up in its pocket. China already leads Germany in one crucial aspect of manufacturing that is digitalization. This is not traditionally a country that has been closely associated with digital innovation, it's going to be a big challenge across a whole range of domains. Look at carmakers, and it's, you know traditionally engineers have fundamentally been the controllers of the car manufacturers who make components, fitting them together, making them look beautiful assembling them. The digital skillset has traditionally taken a backseat, and that's going to have to change, it's not just Germany's car industry that needs to modernize. Before the pandemic, two-thirds of German businesses said they still regularly used a fax machine and only 1/3 of German companies have a central digital strategy. Just eight years ago, Angela Merkel became a meme when she referred to the internet as "Neuland", the German for uncharted territory. The next government is probably going to have to be a lot more digitally savvy than the ones that Angela Merkel has led for the last 16 years, and it's going to have to do a hell of a lot more to translate the rhetoric on digitalization into the reality of fostering genuine change in the country which has been devoid for the last couple of decades.

But there is even a greater challenge that could define Germany's global relevance, here Germany's car industry is a micro cause as to why the country will have to shift. Traditional forms of power will need to be replaced, for cars that mean a risk to go electric. Oliver Zipse took over as CEO of BMW in 2019, he is overseeing one of the biggest shifts in the company's history that is a commitment to battery-powered cars. The whole car industry is launching a lot of electric vehicles now and BMW is at the forefront of that hence they need to speed up their efforts to keep up with the electro-mobility demand. It's a big market developing, and yet they want to increase their profitability and with the right set of components, products. Climate change has forced this shift to a greener future but it was American, not German engineers that first realized it. Although an early investor in electric technology BMW has now fallen behind rivals in the e-car market, other German carmakers were slower still when it comes to fostering innovation the country is still in second gear. Although disruptive innovation does

exist here, Germany's leaders could do more to nurture it. Sono Motors is a startup based in Munich that is technically a carmaker but their approach is light years away from the traditional brands. What they do is producing an electric vehicle that is equipped with solar cells. They are one of several developers around the world trying to get a solar-powered vehicle to market, and their car, the Sion can share power with the grid and other cars and comes with ridesharing software built-in. They claim that they're the only car company that thinks the industry should be selling fewer cars and their approach could upend the industry because their ethos is emblematic of a new way of German thinking. Sono Motors sees themselves as mobility service providers which are not only about the car but it is about the whole new mobility concept, they are providing right from carsharing, ridesharing, power-sharing, a car itself, solar integration, solar technology they sell to others. This whole new insight on how we think mobility should appear in the time to come.

Small companies like Sono have the vision for a greener future but Germany's politics may make it hard to realize. One of the challenges I think that you are going to see in Germany is that the next coalition is probably going to be made up of three different parties that may well have very different ideas about how to manage the climate transition. The sort of consensus-oriented approach that's deeply ingrained in Germany and may not look like it is particularly well suited to manage this extraordinary industrial transition that we're going to have to bring about in the years ahead. So that is going to mean a very, very big role for the next chancellor. As Germany endeavors to digitize continue, the new leader should plan for a workforce in need of upskilling. Carmakers are going to have a massive ramp-up of jobs in the battery-manufacturing sector, massive demand for coders' digital skills, and a concomitant decline in the push for engineering skills that we've seen. As the Chinese stretch, Germany will have to be more careful about whom it connives with. One of the things I think, for example, that you're going to see in the next legislative period is a real investment in Europe's ability to stand on its own two feet to ensure that it is not excessively exposed to the risks that could come from a stepping-up of the strategic competition between America and China. Angela Merkel was careful not to scare voters with the talk of transformation that's left Germany's new leaders with a lot to do. Germany has to do better, right? They have those exceedingly large companies, those vast players who aren't the

disrupter, the driver behind innovation. Disruption always comes from the new and young companies which drive change. German startups rarely grow into vast tech companies without making changes Germany risks losing competitiveness throughout its economy. The ability to face the future "zukunftsfaehigkeit", lots of people looking at these challenges are starting to wonder how "Zukunftsfaehig" Germany is going to be a big challenge not only for the next chancellor but for the government that he or she is going to lead because a lot of people think that. Germany isn't ready, and that it will need to act promptly across a whole range of domains to meet these confrontations.